

Application of Geotextiles in Riverbank Erosion Protection – A Review

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Abstract:

Rivers, except when flowing through well-defined narrow sections confined by high and stiff banks, have caused problems of flooding, change of course, banks erosion etc. Bank erosion can lead to large amount of losses in terms of human life and other utilities. Hence bank protection measures which aim at maintaining the stability of the cross section of river against the action of water is necessary. Commonly used bank protection measures are groins, revetment, riprap etc. Even though they have proven to be effective, most of them are costly and causes environmental issues. Geotextiles have come to play an increasingly important role in civil engineering and are being used for river bank protection. Geotextiles consisting of woven mats, rolls or bags of natural fibres are placed on the bank surface or bank toe to prevent fluvial scour and the removal of fines from the bank face. Coir (coconut fiber) geotextiles are now being used as popular solution for erosion control, slope stabilization and bioengineering, due to the fabric's substantial mechanical strength and its applicability to conserve soil and moisture. Coir geotextiles are better preferred compared to other natural materials owing to their properties like durability, strength, hairy surface etc. Since Kerala state is an abundant source of coconut trees, coir geotextiles are available at low cost. Coco logs are long knotted coir nettings filled with coir fibre. They are 100 % natural material and biodegradable, has high tensile strength, high water absorbency, is easy to install and is eco- friendly. This review paper focusses on study of various techniques used in riverbank protection.

Keywords: Geotextiles, Geobags, Soil erosion, river training work, various techniques

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1. Introduction

Riverbank erosion is a significant environmental issue that not only affects the stability of riverbanks but also poses a threat to nearby infrastructure and ecosystems. Traditional methods of erosion protection, such as riprap and concrete structures, are often costly, time-consuming, and environmentally intrusive. However, the application of geotextiles has emerged as a viable and sustainable solution to mitigate riverbank erosion. Geotextiles are permeable fabrics made from synthetic materials or natural fibers, designed to stabilize soil and prevent erosion. They can be used in a variety of applications, including road construction, landfills, and coastal protection. In the context of riverbank erosion, geotextiles offer several advantages over traditional methods. Firstly, geotextiles act as a soil filter, allowing water to pass through while retaining the soil particles. This prevents the scouring effect of water currents on the riverbank, reducing erosion. The fabric's permeability also promotes the growth of vegetation, which further strengthens the soil and adds to its stability. Additionally, geotextiles provide a physical barrier between the water and the soil, protecting against wave action and hydraulic forces. By absorbing and dissipating the energy of flowing water, they reduce the impact on the riverbank, minimizing erosion. Furthermore, geotextiles are flexible and adaptable, making them suitable for various riverbank profiles and conditions. They can be easily installed and customized to fit the shape and slope of the riverbank, allowing for a seamless integration with the surrounding environment. This flexibility also allows for the preservation of natural habitats and ecosystems, unlike concrete or riprap structures. Another advantage of geotextiles is their longevity. Unlike traditional erosion protection methods that may deteriorate over time, geotextiles are highly durable and resistant to ultraviolet radiation, chemicals, and biological degradation.

2. Cost considerations in Geotextiles

In terms of cost-effectiveness, geotextiles offer significant advantages. Compared to riprap or concrete structures, the materials and installation of geotextiles are generally less expensive. The lightweight and compact nature of geotextiles also make transportation and handling easier and more economical. Moreover, geotextiles have a lower

carbon footprint compared to traditional erosion protection methods. The manufacturing process of geotextiles requires less energy and produces fewer greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, their use promotes sustainable land management practices, as they work in harmony with the natural environment and provide opportunities for vegetation growth. However, it is essential to note that the successful application of geotextiles in riverbank erosion protection requires proper design, installation, and maintenance. Site-specific considerations, such as soil type, water flow, and vegetation, should be taken into account during the planning phase. Regular inspection and maintenance of geotextiles are also necessary to ensure their continued effectiveness.

3. Work carried out by various researchers

The feasibility study of Geobags shows that a heap of Geobags of different sizes placed along the bank just below low water would launch when undercut by erosion and cover the eroding area with a 0.9 m thick layer of protection. Divers' observations clearly showed that this did not happen. The coverage was either by single bags or sometimes lumpy with bare patches. The smallest bags disappeared. Clearly adaptations were needed. For predominantly construction purposes, single-size Geobags are favorable so only 126 kg. bags will be used for future work in Jamuna River. The smaller size of 78 kg is proposed for smaller rivers. If there is to be a mix, it will be with the 78- and 126-kg bags. The protective system was to remain Geobags revetment protection below low water level and concrete blocks or interconnected systems such as grout-filled mattresses above low water. A multi-step implementation system combining a fast response to erosion threat and an optimized use of bags has been developed and implemented that has provided satisfactory protection [1].

Figure 1: Different types of Geobags placed as temporary wave protection.

Jute Geotextiles fabrics treated with 0.5% isothiazolinone and 1.0% fluorocarbon derivatives show higher water repellency as well as rot resistant characteristics. These improved functional properties of treated jute Geotextiles are advantageous in terms of its end use in river bank protection. It is observed in river bank simulation test that the life of treated jute Geotextiles under combined soil-water ambience is 600-700 days. Major functional properties desired for jute Geotextiles such as strength, elongation, porometry, water permittivity and rod puncture resistance etc. do not alter much due to such chemical treatment. All these positive attributes of specially treated jute Geotextiles suggest its effective application in river bank protection [2].

River training work is a complex and intricate process. Proper river training and protective work help protect the land of thousands of people in a densely populated country. Success of such works depend on a number of factors which should be carefully addressed [3].

Figure 2: Counting and lengthwise placing of filled geo-bags

The use of a thickly woven coir geotextile for construction of mud wall has been demonstrated in the Kuttanad area, which represents a typical peat soil. Besides it has been proved to act as good separator and drainage filter also. The strength of soil has been found to increase in course of time as the organic skeleton has remained in place in compressed form that acts as a filter cake providing sustainable protection to the streambank. Local vegetation grown over the embankment has been providing extra protection against erosion of mud wall. This treatment opens up new avenues for the application of coir geotextiles that could be applied in low-lying areas all over the world. It is seen that even after eight years the mud wall is intact and it is performing well. The tremendous strength and biodegradability of coir makes it suitable to various new areas of application in the soil bioengineering [4].

Figure 3: Close up view of applied coir geotextile on the stream bank

An analysis of the results of a distorted-scale laboratory investigation of geobag revetment performance, with particular emphasis on complete failure processes. Such analysis helps to predict the behaviour of a geobag revetment while it is exposed to different flow conditions and/or construction specifications. However, the distorted-physical model used for laboratory experiments had the limitations as Scale effects that existed due to the physical model. The fixed-bed nature of the experimental work, which helped isolate the impact of hydrodynamic loadings, meant that the impact of toe scour could not be incorporated [5].

Figure 4: Pull-out of a geobag from a layer close to water surface

Physical model studies were conducted on an undistorted river model to study the efficacy of coir geotextiles as a river bank protection measure using woven coir geotextile mat and cocologs. The placement of geotextiles increased the depth of water and decreased the velocity of flow compared to the unprotected bank (UB). Cocolog acted as soft toe armour and protected the side slopes by retaining the sediments above it. Cocolog has the ability of reducing water velocity by absorbing water and acting as a semi pervious media. Geotextile mat acted as check dams and arrested the migration of soil particles by flowing water. The best erosion protection was produced when woven coir geotextile mat was placed over the side slopes with one cocolog at bank toe as the volume of erosion was least in this case [6].

Figure 5 : River model with geotextile mat and cocolog (a) before experiment (b) after experiment

The study on the effect of installation of river bank protection measure along with bed protection using geotextile bags in river Jia Bharali has revealed the following important conclusions:

1. The protection work has successfully diverted the river from the protected bank and resulted in siltation creating a sand bar extending to a distance nearly 30 times that of the width of the launching apron.
2. Although flow of the river is diverted from the bank in the protected stretch the diverted steam has sharply come back towards the bank just beyond the downstream end of the protection work, thus, rendering the bank downstream of the protection work vulnerable to erosion.
3. The poor geotechnical properties of the bank subsoil has made it further susceptible to erosion.
4. The protection work in its downstream has adversely affected the very river bank causing erosion and gradual shifting of the major stream of the river into the bank within a period of 3 years [7].

Figure 6: Technical details of the bank protection work installed

Government policies and frameworks can be a microcosm for similar such endeavours, particularly in the rural global south. Government policies and frameworks and local stakeholder involvements that facilitate such an undertaking, with particular emphasis on the organizational workflow and the ground-level perception of such endeavours, as these are crucial to the success and effectiveness of such schemes. The marked successes achieved through the use of the Vetiver grass in abating erosion and the hindrances encountered in implementing such mitigation projects are outlined, along with the importance of such community based approaches to river management and monitoring [8].

Figure 7: Aligning bamboo geogrids with bank geometry

High performance geotextile is always a crucial direction of geotextile development. At present, it is mainly to add additives and modify geotextile to make up for the performance defects of geotextile. Secondly, the geotextile with excellent properties can be made from high performance fiber, such as glass fiber or basalt fiber. In the future, it is possible to design geotextiles with unique and excellent properties by applying nanofibers to geotextiles. Application of intelligent geotextiles in geotechnical engineering is need of the time. [9].

Figure 8: Intelligent geotextiles for installation

An application of woven type geo-textile with sufficient pores to dissipate pore pressure can restore the foundation material. Above the geo-textile sheet riprap pitching of 15 cm thick gravel of 30 mm to 125 mm sizes and more than 20 cm thick water front stone boulders above 200 mm size may be suited to protect the embankment at the study section. The geo-textile reinforced revetment may act as a rescue against the alarming situation of cutting and erosion in the river. The protection has to be done up to scour depth also as per provision of relevant codes available and others. The normal scour depth calculated at section of km 37 and km 62 is 5.4 m and 6.4 m, respectively [10].

Figure 9: River bank embankment-Groyne layout-repelling type

4. Conclusion

Geotextiles are commonly used in riverbank erosion protection due to their effectiveness in stabilizing soil and preventing erosion. Some applications of geotextiles in riverbank erosion protection include:

Slope Stabilization: Geotextiles can be used to stabilize the slopes of riverbanks by preventing soil erosion caused by water flow. They are placed alongside the slope and act as a barrier that holds the soil in place, reducing the risk of slope failure.

i. Bank Protection: Geotextiles can be used to protect riverbanks from erosion caused by wave action or high water flows. They are placed along the waterline or submerged in the riverbed to prevent scour and stabilize the bank. Geotextile tubes or mattresses filled with soil can also be used as revetment systems to protect the bank from erosion.

ii. Filtration and Drainage: Geotextiles can be used to facilitate proper drainage of water from the soil, preventing saturation and reducing the risk of erosion. They can be used as a filter fabric to allow water to drain while preventing the loss of fine soil particles.

iii. Vegetation Support: Geotextiles can be used to support vegetation growth on riverbanks. They create a stable environment for plant roots to anchor and grow, reducing the risk of bank erosion. Geotextiles can also protect newly planted seedlings from being washed away by water flow.

iv. Sediment Control: Geotextiles can be used to control sediment runoff from construction sites or disturbed areas near riverbanks. They can be installed as silt fences or sediment barriers to prevent sediment-laden water from entering the river and causing bank erosion.

- v. **Geobags:** Geotextiles can be fabricated into geobags, which are flexible containers filled with soil or other materials. Geobags can be used in riverbank erosion protection by creating a permeable barrier that stabilizes the bank and prevents soil loss while allowing water to pass through.

Overall, the application of geotextiles in riverbank erosion protection provides a cost-effective and environmentally friendly solution to prevent erosion and maintain the stability of riverbanks.

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